

THE PURPOSE OF MEDIA COMPETENCE IN ELEMENTARY GRADES IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Abstract. This article explores the role and importance media competence in improving the quality of education in elementary school. It also recommended the shortcomings and problems that we currently facing and necessary actions to be taken.

Key words: primary classes, media competence, didactic education, animations, interactive, component, digital, effective, teaching process.

Introduction. Currently, the school is on the way to the formation of an educational information system. With the development of technological progress, the process of obtaining information has changed. The printed word genre is being changed. Media education included in the school curriculum makes it possible to revive the education system in the direction of democratization of the educational process. Students master technical communication tools, develop a conscious perception and critical attitude towards media reporting. In other words, the content of education, methods, forms of work, types of lessons are updated. There was a need to apply new technologies, create a media environment, increase the culture of the audience.

Materials. The comprehensive use of media technologies in the educational process helps to humanize education, increase educational efficiency, increase the share of independent work in educational activities, activate educational activities by introducing research features that are decisive for the development of creative personality. The modern educational system should not only give the ability to adequately perceive information, but also teach how to perceive it, work with it, apply it to certain life situations and interpret this information. Thus, new knowledge is born on the basis of existing knowledge.

Methods. It is also necessary to develop a certain amount of skills and skills in order to work with various sources of knowledge in the student, not to repeat knowledge, but to expand them, to educate the ability to apply them in different life situations. It is very important to form your own attitude to facts, problems, listen to others, find ways to solve problems together. In the era of dynamic changes, the construction of education by translating information by the teacher becomes ineffective, so the main thing is to form the ability to learn independently.

Thus, critical thinking is not a separate skill, but a complex of skills and skills that are gradually formed in the process of development and learning of the child. If in classes children are not passive listeners, but constantly actively seek information, associate what they have learned with their practical experience, compare the acquired knowledge with other works in this area and other areas of knowledge (in familiar terms, they independently establish internal and interdisciplinary connections). In addition, students should learn to question the reliability and reliability of information, check the logic of evidence, draw conclusions, create new examples for the use of theoretical knowledge, make decisions, study the causes and consequences of various phenomena (and teachers should help them).

Results. It is absolutely impossible to imagine the life of a modern person without interaction with the media. Mass media has penetrated into all areas of people's lives. Media plays a huge role in human life: in the exchange of information between people, in the upbringing and upbringing of children, as well as in the socialization of the younger generation. In this regard, the role of media education is especially large. Media education is a current and very popular topic, but has not yet been sufficiently studied, both practical and theoretical. Media education-the process of personality development with the help of the media and based on materials with the aim of teaching the culture of communication with the media, creative communication skills, critical thinking, the formation of skills for the full perception, analysis and assessment of media text, various forms of self-expression with the help of media technologies.

The main goals of Media education:

- development of the ability to search, perceive and process information, understanding the hidden meaning of the message;
- formation of critical thinking skills, expression of one's position;
- develop effective communication skills using media tools.

The main tasks of Media education. The scale of the influence of the media on various spheres of life is growing day by day. This creates new problems for the educational system, requires a person not only modern technical means and the ability to work with them, but also a certain level of critical thinking (the ability to interpret media messages, understand various media texts), independent creative work skills associated with the search, processing and presentation of information materials, etc. Currently, many schools are equipped with multimedia equipment (interactive whiteboards, consoles, projectors, digital microscope), a multimedia library.

Discussion. What does Media education give to an elementary school pupils?

The result of Media education is media literacy. Prominent scholars describe media literacy as "the ability to adequately perceive, interpret, evaluate, and create media texts. Media education increases the cognitive activity of students, develops the ability to translate information from one sign language to another, use new information from references, media, the internet, translate it in the form of messages, lectures, oral and written messages, presentations, projects, videos. Starting from elementary school, the child learns to be a translator, and he must go through the following stages:

- see;
- markup;
- write;
- create media text, share information.

The teacher comes to her aid, she develops the ability to justify, tell, prove, discuss the qualities of critical thinking through communication. And by analysis, synthesis, comparison, generalization, classification, the reader draws his conclusions.

Media security. A modern teacher should not only have methodological knowledge of media education, but also know how to protect a child from media risk, warn. Often, children take what they see on TV and on the Internet at face value. Due to their age, lack of life experience and knowledge of media literacy, they do not always recognize the manipulative

methods used in advertising and other information presentation, do not analyze the level of reliability of information and the authenticity of its sources.

Conclusion. Media education is an integral part of the educational process, since it allows the teacher to diversify the tasks, methods and forms of presenting information in the educational process, use computer programs that include a wide range of exercises: training (for presenting material), training (for practicing skills and skills), text (for testing knowledge). They make it possible to strengthen the independent work of students, choose information, work at a pace in accordance with the level of knowledge of students, develop critical thinking of each individual.

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